

Incidence of Breeding Problems in Haryana Cattle

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Abstract The objectives were to characterize repeat breeding and anoestrus in dairy cows. Data from 641 calving records 193 adult cows were enrolled and maintained. at Govt. livestock farm, Hastinapur, India. Data were classified into five lactations and four seasons over a period of 18 years. Of the 641 observations, the rate of anoestrus and repeat breeding was 24.96 percent and 12.48 percent, respectively. Period and season of calving of calving was significant ($P < 0.05$) influence on anoestrus and repeat breeding in this herd. The incidence of anoestrus and repeat breeding was found highest 32.12 percent and 16.06 percent respectively. Among first calf heifers, same trend was showed in summer season for those traits. The incidence of repeat breeding in India has been reported from 5.3 to 33.33 percent in cattle (sexena, 2004)

Keywords Non-Genetic Factors, Repeat Breeding, Anoestrus, Haryana Cattle.

Introduction Reproductive problems affect the herd life, reproduction efficiency of cows and economy of dairy herds and are responsible for culling of the cows. It has been observed that indigenous breed are less susceptible for the reproduction problems as compared to the crossbred cows.

Aim of study

In this present investigation two common reproductive disorders as anoestrus and repeat breeding are studied. Anoestrus is characterized by an abnormally prolonged period of gonadal quiescence in which there is absence of sexual cycle and heat symptoms. or also failed to show anoestrus within 90 days postpartum. Whereas, in repeat breeding, the cows did not conceive with 3. insemination and it is one of the most important fertility problem faced by veterinarians. Fertilization failure and early embryonic mortality are major cause of repeat breeding problem.

Review of Literature

Identification of non-genetic factors influencing breeding problems will facilitate developing breeding and management strategies for realizing higher intensity and increased accuracy of selection of elite cows in the herd (Balasundaram B. 2010).

Methodology The data were collected from the history sheet regarding health register, culling reports, mortality and fertility registers of 641 calving records of 193 adult Haryana breed cows enrolled at Govt. livestock farm, Hastinapur in the Northern India, The data were spread over a period of 18 years of calving from 1992 to 2009, which were classified into four periods, four seasons and five parity numbers. This was done to estimate the incidence of reproductive problems in different level these non-genetic factors and then to conduct the analysis of variance to know the significance of the differences in the incidence. The following mathematical model was used to conduct the analysis of variance.

$$Y_{ijkl} = \mu + Li + Pj + Sk + e_{ijkl}$$

where,

μ = overall mean

Li = effect of i^{th} lactation ($i = 1 \dots \dots \dots 5$)

pj = effect of j^{th} period ($j = 1 \dots \dots \dots 4$)

Sk = effect of k^{th} season ($K = 1 \dots \dots \dots 4$)

e_{ijkl} = random error specific to the particular observations.

Result and Discussion Incidence of anoestrus

The result the present study on the average incidence of anoestrus and repeat breeding cows have been presented in Table 1. The overall incidence of anoestrus Cows in this herd was 24.96 percent. Thus about one fourth of the total cows not comes in heat within 90 days of calving, Almost similar estimates from 22.40 percent to 27.50 percent were reported by Patel etal (2007), Bhattacharya and Buchoo (2008) and Kumar etal (2018) in Gujrat and Kashmir region. On the contrary Sangeeta etal (2002) and Sardar etal (2010) reported the incidence of anoestrus to only 15.6 percent and 20.4 percent respectively.

The incidence of anoestrus was found highest 32.12 percent among first calf heifers and there was a decreasing trend with increase in parity order, Being only 17.64 percent in fifth and later lactations. The statistical analysis of data presented in Table 2 had shown that the parity of calving had significant effect on the incidence of anoestrus. This was in close agreement with Khan et al. (2016) The higher incidence of anoestrus in first calves may be due to that most of the part of their energy is utilized for milk production and in building up their body as a protective mechanism to conserve their own body reserve and left out energy inadequate for performing reproductive functions.

The period of calving caused very little variation (23.9 to 28.4 percent) in anoestrus. It indicate that the period of calving had no effect on the incidence of anoestrus (Table 2). Bhattacharya and Bachoo (2008). have also found that the incidence of anoestrus varied among years from 20.6 to 34.6 percent.

The incidence of anoestrus was high in cows calved during summer season (33.3 percent) Table 1, and low in those calved in rainy season (18.7 percent), season of calving had significant ($P < 0.05$) effect (Table 2) on incidence of anoestrus. Balasundran etal (2010) had the similar observation in crossbred cows. Kumar etal (2014) stated that the environmental stress (Extreme hot and cold) affect development of follicle and manifestation of oestrus in cattle. Ovarian activity is greatly reduced by heat stress and manifested in the form of anoestrus.

Table:1 Average incidence of reproductive problems (%) in relation to different non-genetic factors.

Effects	No. observations	Anoestrus	Repeat Breeding
Overall	642	24.96 (160)	12.48 (8)
Parity			
1	193	32.12 (62)	16.06(31)
2	153	24.83 (38)	11.76(18)
3	116	22.41(26)	12.07(14)
4	77	20.77(16)	11.68(9)
5	102	17.64 (18)	7.84(8)
Period			
1	74	28.38(21)	13.51(10)
2	167	25.15(42)	12.57(21)
3	226	23.89(54)	11.94(27)
4	174	24.71(43)	12.64(22)
Season			
Winter	298	24.83(74)	13.75(41)
Summer	135	33.33(45)	16.29(22)
Rainy	139	18.70(26)	6.47(9)
Autumn	69	21.74(15)	11.59(8)

*Figure in parenthesis are the number of affected cows.

Table:2 ANOVA showing the effect of different non-genetic factors on reproductive problems.

S.V	DF	Anoestrus	Repeat Breeding
Lactations	4	0.5565*	0.3669*
Periods	3	0.0121	0.0122
Seasons	3	0.5208*	0.2807*
Error	630	0.1853	0.1098

* $P < 0.05$

Incidence of Repeat breeding

The overall incidence of repeat breeding in this hard was observed to be 12.48 percent (Table1) Almost similar findings have been reported by Thakur et a.l (2006 a) 12.41 percent, Singh et al. (2008) 14.75 percent, Sardar etal (2010) 12.80 percent, Yusuf etal (2010) 14.0 percent in Indian of breeds of cows, whereas, the incidence of

repeat breeding from 12 to 20 percent was reported by sharma and Karwani (2003) and Kaur et al.(2011) in central zone of Punjab in Indian and crossbred cows.

The incidence of repeat breeding was found highest in the first calvers than older cows (Table 1). Statistically the parity of calving had significant ($P<0.05$) effect on the incidence of repeat breeding (Table 2). It was indicated that the higher incidence of matritis, anatomical hormonal and management practices may be occurred. About 40 percent of the repeat breeder cows are due to fertilization failure, Fertilization failure triggered due to abnormalities in ovulation (wodaje and Mekurea, 2016), On the contrary, low incidence of repeat breeding in heifer calving had been reported by Arun and singh (2009), in Haryana cows.

The cows calved among different periods showed the incidence of repeat breeding from 11.94 to 13.51 percent (Table 1) and exert non- significant influence on that traits (Table 2). This was supported by Sangeeta et al. (2002). Whereas on the contrary, Bhattachary and Buchoo (2008) observed the significant influence on such trait.

It was further observed that the incidence of repeat breeding was highest among the cows calved during summer season (16.29 percent) and lowest was during rainy season (6.47 percent), Season of calving had significant effect on incidence of repeat breeding. The high incidence of repeat breeding during summer season may be due to high temperature which depressed feed Consumption, hormonal dysfunction, nutritional inadequacies and improper management practices resulting in the reduction of conception rate (Malik et al 2019). Season of calving had significant influence on the incidence of repeat breeding had reported by Balasundran et al (2010) in crossbred Cows.

Conclusion The overall incidence of anoestrus and Repeat breeding was 24.96 percent and 12:48 percent respectively. The incidence for these traits was highest in first calvers and there was a decreasing trend with increase in parity orders. The parity and season of calving had significant ($P<0.05$) influence on the anoestrus and Repeat breeding On the contrary, the period of calving was exert non-significant influence on anoestrus and repeat breeding, Highest incidence for anoestrus and repeat breeding was estimated in summer season whereas, lowest was in rainy season.

- References**
1. Arum, K; and Sligh, U. Fertility status of Haryana cows. Indian Vet. J. 2009; 86; 807-809.
 2. Balasundran, B; Dongre, VB; Gupta; A.K.; Mohanty;, T, K, Sharma P.L; Khate, K. and Singh RK; Wayamba J. of Anim. Sci. 2010; 11-23 Vol. 2, 46-48.
 3. Bhattacharys, H, K and Buchoo BA. Incidence of reproductive disorders of cattle in Kashmir Valley, Indian J. Dairy Sci. 2008; 61: 165-167.
 4. Kaur I; Dhindra ss; Harpreet, K. and Prabhjot, S. various constraints of dairy farming in central zone of Punjab. J. of Dairying food and Home sciences, 2011; 30, 242-245,
 5. Khan, M.H. Manoj K. and Pramod. Reproductive disorder in dairy cattle under semi intensive system of rearing in North Eastern India. Vet. World. 2016; 9(5):512-510.
 6. Kumar, P; Purohit, G.N. and Mehta J.S. Incidence of reproductive disorders in dairy cows. Indian Polivet. 2018; 19(1): 29-32.
 7. Kumar, P.R; Singh, S.K; Knorche S.D Govindaraju; C.S; Behere BK; Shukla SN; Kumar, H. and Agrawal, SK. Anoestrus in cattle and buffalo; Indian Perspective. Advances in Animal and veterinary sciences, 2014, 2(3): 124-138.
 8. Malik, M.H; verma, H.K and Sharma, SK, Prevalence risk factor and constraints in control of repeat breeding in dairy animals of Punjab. Indian J. of Anim. Sci. 2019, 89(8):837-842.
 9. Patel, P.; Dhani A.J; Sarvaiya, N.P. and Kavani, F.S. Monitoring postpartum period in Holstein Friesian cow through plasma progesterone profile with and without hormone therapy. Indian J. of Anim. Sci. 2007; 77 (1): 3-9.
 10. Sangeeta, C: Ali, S.Z and Kuralkar S.V. Incidence of reproductive disorders in crossbred cows. Indian J. Dairy Sci. 2002; 55(5): 313-315,
 11. Sardar, M.J.U; Moni, M.I.Z and Aktar S. Prevalence of reproductive disorders of crossbreed cows in Rajshahi district of Bangladesh SARC J. Agric. 2010.; 8(2): 65-75.
 12. Sexena, M.S. In Proc, National Symposium on conservation and propagation in indigenous breed of cattle and buffaloes held at Pantnager UK. 2004; 26-28.
 13. Sharma, J, K., and Karwani A. Incidence and epidemiology of and abortion and repeat breeding in bovines at dairy farms. in Punjab, 11th international symposium of the world association of veterinary laboratory diagnosticians and OIE seminar in Biotechnology. 2003.
 14. Singh, J; Dadarwal, D; Honperkhe, M, and Kumar A. Incidence of various etiological factors responsible for repeat breeding syndrome in cattle and buffaloes. The International J. Vet. Med. 2008; 6(1): 1-6.
 15. Thakur, S.; Singh, M. and Vasishta, N.K. Study on etiology of repeat breeding in M..P. Punjab Vet. J. 2006a; 4:27-29.
 16. Wodaje, H.B. and Mekuria TA, Risk factor of repeat breeding in dairy cattle. Advances in Biological Research, 2016, 10(4) 213-221.
 17. Yusuf M; Nakao, T; Binalka, R.M.S. Kamari, R; Gautam, G; Long ST, Yoshida, C; Kocke, K and Mayashi A. Reproductive performance. of repeat breeding in dairy herds. Theriogenology. 2010;73:1220-1229.

